

Dedicated e-Drive family with efficiency optimization and embedded cooling.

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1.1 Electrification - Overview & Market

Analysis

Abstract: Performance of an e-Motor, Inverter and reducer integrated e-Drive system directly influences the overall performance of an electric vehicle. The electric motor windings heat up when operated under extreme load and hence, reducing the efficiency of the vehicle. Inverters generate heat during power conversion, while suffering power losses and damages at higher internal temperatures. As such, an effective cooling system is essential for the EV propulsion system, not only to the battery packs but also to the e-Drive system in order to ensure efficient operation, boost the performance, and maximize the lifetime of the electrical components and vehicle. In addition, e-Motor sizing directly depends on the cooling system that allows to lower the vehicle weight and increase the energy efficiency. This paper investigates a design of a highly efficient e-Drive system with a fully integrated cooling system and advanced cybersecurity features based on Plug and Play approach. The Gearbox Motor Generator (GMG) is directly mounted to the reducer to ensure high powertrain efficiency and optimize the NVH performance. Cooling control system is completely embedded into the inverter that enables it to control the liquid flow rate based on the information from 7 temperature sensors mounted to the e-Motor, inverter and heatsink. The mixture of water and glycol is used as coolant because it offers higher continuous torque than oil and air-cooled systems. The cooling box, made up of a heatsink and a cooling pump, is connected to the inverter and e-Motor in series via cooling pipes. Benchmarked designs and existing components such as the PMSM machine, inverter, reducer, heatsink, water pumps are reused to optimize the cost of the e-Drive system. A 1-D simulation performed in Modelon revealed that the proposed cooling system is sufficient enough to compensate the e-Drive thermal losses of 1000 [W] with margin at 40° C ambient temperature and 1.5 [m/s] air mass flow rate in WMTC2 driving cycle.

Keywords: Electric Vehicles (EV), e-Drive, e-Access, Small Mobility Motor Generator (SMMG), Gearbox Motor Generator (GMG), Water Cooled EV propulsion system, Embedded Cooling Control system, Thermal Efficiency Optimization.

The global automotive industry is at a crossroad as the global vehicle fleet is in a rapid transition phase from ICE vehicles to zero-emission vehicles. The high fuel consumption and exhaust emissions of ICE engines have exacerbated the global energy crisis and environmental pollution. The legislative measures imposed by the governments of economic giants like the USA, China, EU, Japan, India are accelerating electrification. The emission standards imposed by the governments of these leading countries are expected to be emulated by other countries across Asia, Europe and Africa in near future as the consequences of climate change are becoming more severe. With higher requirements for fuel economy and emission standards, automotive companies are updating their traditional vehicles and developing new energy-saving and environment friendly vehicles.

While the current EV market still accounts for a single digit percentage of a global passenger car sales, several countries, especially across Europe, have made huge strides towards a cleaner future in 2020 and 2021 Q1. While Norway is by far the country with the highest share of electric cars in total passenger car sales, no country comes even closer to China in terms of absolute market size.

Figure 1: Worldwide EV market, 2021 Q1 [Canalys]

The stock price of Tesla skyrocketed by 740% in 2020 and the momentum is continuing in 2021. While Tesla is leading the worldwide EV market share by 15%, several other automakers are shifting their business model to include EV production.

1. Introduction

Figure 2: Worldwide EV sales, 2021 Q1 [Canalys]

The new car sales of EV are increasing significantly and is forecasted to reach close to 60% by 2040, while 33% of the global car fleet is predicted to be electric by the same time. EV production will gain more momentum as the market shares of HEV and PHEV are also forecasted to decline from 2030, following the ICEs ban roadmap and green deal measures to combat climate change.

Figure 3: Worldwide electrification forecast scenario [Bloomberg New Energy Finance, 2017]

Besides the momentum of switching to a new architecture that goes with the climate goal, constraints relative to e-Motors are defying the design of electric propulsion systems. Indeed, due to limited space and weight in vehicles, high performance and compact motors are strongly required. Fortunately, the technological advancements in materials and technologies have enabled the development of high specific power motors. A turning point in the electric machinery domain has been registered during the last decade, highlighted by the rising interest in developing electric vehicles. While propulsion electrification is considered a promising solution for environmental pollution, electric motors in the automotive domain are still constrained by several issues such as performance, weight, cooling, safety, external conditions, etc. Thermal management is one of the major constraints of EV development. EVs need to not only cool the Batteries, but also the electric motor under different temperature conditions that directly impacts the e-Drive efficiency and EVs performance. High temperature affects the motor output torque, cogging torque, power, overload characteristics and

motor life [1]. Thermal runaways of the motor can even cause the essential transformation of the motor insulation material to lose its insulation ability, reducing the strength and hardness of the motor metal components. This paper focuses on the thermal management of an e-Drive system that mainly includes e-Motor, inverter, DC/DC converter, actuators, reducer, differential and cooling system.

The thermal management technologies implemented in electric propulsion systems are predominantly based on air, oil and water-cooled technologies. Compared with other cooling technologies, liquid cooling is widely used due to its high cooling efficiency, easy maintenance and technological maturity. Moreover, water cooled systems provide higher continuous torque than air and oil cooled systems [2].

1.2 Previous Works

Valeo-SVA's e-Drive system is named 'eAccess' and they are codified in 2 different generations (Gen) based on the technological upgrades, principally, by the connection between e-Machine and the reducer.

1.2.1 eAccess Gen 1 (9 kWc)

Figure 4: eAccess Generation 1

eAccess Gen 1 was an air cooled, wound-rotor synchronous motor based 48V BSG solution with output power range of 9kW (continuous) and 13 kW (peak). It was a cost-efficient solution, had simple system and mechanical interfaces and could provide flexible gear ratio options, thanks to the belt drive. However, the lower output power and powertrain efficiency (~82%) limited the potential BEV applications because of the thermal management technology based on air. The lower NVH performance due to the belt drive was another major consideration that originated the need of next generation eAccess.

1.2.2 eAccess Gen 2

eAccess Gen2 was introduced replacing the belt connection by the direct drive between e-Machine and reducer. Valeo-SVA has developed multiple power range eAccess Gen2 solutions to well answer the customer needs and to cover the wide range of electrification solutions.

a) eAccess Gen 2-DD (9 kWc)

Figure 5: eAccess Gen2- Direct Drive (9 kW)

eAccess Gen 2(9 kW) is a direct drive version of eAccess Gen 1 with some additional features such as cybersecurity and safety functions. The direct drive significantly accounts for the improvement on NVH performances, transmission losses and packaging. However, the factors like thermal losses, IP level (IP25), powertrain efficiency etc. are still unimproved because it is still an air-cooled solution.

b) eAccess Gen 2-DD (4 kWc)

Valeo-SVA introduced another eAccess Gen2 with 48V SMMG based on the PMSM motor for the small mobilities(2W/3W) with the output power range of 4 kW (continuous) and 8 kW (peak). Powertrain efficiency is significantly enhanced up-to 90% by the use of a PMSM motor. it's a modular powertrain concept with 2 reducer designs allows it to be applied in 2-wheeler and 3-wheeler requirements. it is still an air-cooled solution; however, the IP level is enhanced to IP67 by modifying the housing design.

Figure 6: eAccess Gen2- Direct Drive, SMMG (4 kW)

This paper proposes an upgraded version of eAccess Gen2 that has significant improvement on cooling system, IP level, Power level, cybersecurity and safety features, cost and application areas.

1.3 Target

Valeo-SVA's aim is to make cost-effective 48V e-Drive powertrain systems for low~mid-range of electrification applications with a high level of efficiency and performance. One of the most important and delicate components to achieve Valeo-SVA's target is the e-Drive cooling system that must guarantee the safe and enough heat dissipation to ensure the efficient operation of the e-Machine, maximize the lifetime of the electrical components and integrity of the e-Drive system. Belted e-Drive solutions are easier to integrate and provide flexible gear ratios, however, potential applications are limited due to poor NVH performance. Air-cooled e-Drive systems have limitations on the potential applications due to lower cooling efficiency that lowers the overall powertrain efficiency.

Target is to design and develop an e-Drive (eAccess) powertrain with the following features:

- **High thermal efficiency:**
 - Water cooling system is integrated within e-Drive.
- **Simple interface and easy integration:**
 - Cooling control unit is embedded in the inverter.
- **High powertrain efficiency and output power:**
 - PMSM motor (13 kWc) is used.
- **NVH Optimization:**
 - Direct drive.
- **New system functions:**
 - implementation of cybersecurity and safety features.
- **Cost optimization:**
 - Reuse of off-the-shelf parts.

Figure 7: Targeted eAccess Powertrain

The major goal is to develop a water-cooled modular e-Drive system that is as simple as an air-cooled e-Drive without any extra cooling control load to the VCU and meets the customer requirements in terms of integration simplicity, cost, performance, efficiency and safety perspectives.

2. Cooling control integrated e-Drive (eAccess Gen 2- DD (13 kWc))

Valeo-SVA developed a cost-efficient eAccess powertrain based on the existing components, benchmarked design and well-known cooling concept. The characteristics of major individual components of the newly developed eAccess powertrain are summarized in this section.

2.1 e-Machine

Figure 8: e-Machine

A 48 [V] GMG based on a highly efficient PMSM motor with the output power range of 13 kWc~17 kWp is used in the proposed eAccess. The PMSM motor is capable of generating torque at zero speed and provides higher torque density. The eAccess power is upgraded by carrying-over in-house major components such as rotor, stator, etc.

2.2 Reducer

Figure 9: Reducer

Off-the-shelf reducer is placed in direct drive connection with e-Machine. It saved the cost, enhanced the efficiency, optimized the NVH performance, as well as lowered the risk of project failure.

2.3 Inverter

Figure 10: Inverter

An additional important function, a cooling control system is embedded in the inverter to control the coolant flow rate depending on the temperature conditions of the e-Drive components. The inverter is compact, efficient and can operate on both motor and generator mode.

2.4 Cooling system

Figure 11: Cooling system

A cooling box is developed by utilizing existing heatsink and a water pump. Cooling pipes coming out of the cooling box are connected to the inverter and e-Machine in series to allow the coolant circulation. Cold water coming from the cooling box first passes through the Inverter, gets warmer, then passes through the e-Machine, gets hotter and returns back to the cooling box. The heat sink then absorbs the heat from the hot water and the cycle continues.

2.4.1 Cooling pump control

Cooling pump is controlled by the cooling control unit embedded in the inverter based on the information from 7 temperature sensors (e-Motor (1), inverter power module (3), inverter heat sink (2), inverter PCB (1)) via CAN communication. The components threshold temperature is predefined in the control system and flow rate control is set up in such a way that coolant flow rate increases when the temperature of the components increases. The pump control is completely transparent to the customers as the cooling pump control unit featuring diagnostic and degraded modes are embedded in the inverter to protect the system and enhance the cooling efficiency.

2.4.2 Cooling system sizing strategy

Figure 12: WMTC2 driving cycle

WMTC2 driving cycle is used as a dimensioning cycle for the cooling system. The average power losses are simulated for WMTC1 & WMTC2 driving cycles and the worst case scenario is referenced to size the cooling system or the heat sink to well compensate for the thermal losses.

Table 1: Average power losses

Reference Driving Cycles	Avg. Power Losses (W)
WMTC1	895.5
WMTC2	969.5

Worst Case

A 1D simulation is then performed in 'Modelon' to size the heat sink with the following conditions:

- **Losses to be resolved: 969.5 watts**
- **Cooling box outlet temperature: ~ 70 °C**
- **heat sink off-the-shelf: 'TAHC Gen2'**
- **inverter and e-Machine in series**
- **in/out temperature as close as possible**

Table 2: Simulation results (Cooling system sizing)

T Air (°C)	40		
Air flow (m/s)	1.5	2	3
Water flow (l/min)	4		
T(water) cooling box inlet	57.8	52.1	46.4
T(water) cooling box outlet	53.8	48.1	42.2

The simulation results shown in Table 2 shows that the cooling system is sufficient to compensate for the thermal losses of 1000 [W] with margin at 40 °C ambient temperature and 1.5 [m/s] air mass flow.

2.5 Smart eAccess control system (Inverter + Cooling control system)

Figure 13: Smart eAccess control system

Liquid flow is controlled by the cooling control unit embedded in the inverter as shown in Figure 13. So, there is no additional cooling control load to the VCU.

2.6 eAccess Gen2- DD (13 kWc)

Figure 14: eAccess Gen2- DD, GMG (13 kW)

Finally, the proposed e-Drive (eAccess Gen2-GMG) is developed by utilizing the major components explained in section 2.1 ~ 2.5 with a simple and integrated cooling system based on plug & play approach. The overall cost of the eAccess is optimized by reusing the inhouse major components.

3. Results

A simulation tool is developed on matlab/simulink to simulate the performance and consumption of the newly developed eAccess and to compare the results with the previous solutions.

3.1 Mechanical Power and Wheel Torque

The performance of the eAccess Gen1 with IBSG and newly developed eAccess Gen2 with GMG at 48V is shown below.

Figure 15: eAccess Gen1 with IBSG

Figure 16: eAccess Ge2 with GMG

It can be observed from Figure 15~16, the newly developed eAccess Gen2 with GMG provides peak mechanical power of nearly 18 [kW] and continuous mechanical power of 12 [kW] that is significantly higher than the peak and continuous mechanical power possible by the eAccess Gen1 with IBSG that are 13.8 [kW] and 9.2 [kW] respectively. Similarly, the peak and continuous wheel torque of 880 [Nm] and 473 [Nm] by the newly developed eAccess are notably higher than the peak and continuous wheel torque possible by eAccess Gen1 with IBSg, that are 686 [Nm] and 245 [Nm].

3.2 Acceleration time and maximum speed

The time taken to reach the speed of 0~80 [kph] and the maximum speed possible by the eAccess Gen1 with IBSG and eAccess Gen2 with GMG are shown below.

Table 3: Acceleration and Max. Speed Comparison

Performances data			
PWT:	iBSG	GMG	Δ(GMG-iBSG)
0 - 45 kph (s)	7.5	5.6	- 25.3 %
0 - 80 kph (s)	28.3	17.8	- 37.1 %
Max Speed (Km/h)	85.5	99.4	+16.2 %

Table 3 shows that the newly developed eAccess with GMG allows it to accelerate faster to reach the targeted speeds compared to the existing solution with IBSG. Similarly, the possible maximum speed is also increased by more than 16% with the proposed eAccess.

3.3 Energy Consumption

The electrical energy consumption by the existing eAccess Gen1 with IBSG and newly developed eAccess Gen2 with GMG in WMTC1 and WMTC2 driving cycles are shown below.

Table 4: Electrical energy consumptions

Cycles simulations				
Cycles	PWT:	iBSG	GMG	Δ(GMG-iBSG)
WMTC 1	Conso with regen (Wh/Km)	59.6	46.8	- 21.5 %
	Conso with regen (kWh/100 Km)	6.0	4.7	-21.7 %
WMTC 2	Conso with regen (Wh/Km)	62.8	50.5	-19.6 %
	Conso with regen (kWh/100 Km)	6.3	5.1	-19.1 %

The results in the above table show that the newly developed eAccess with GMG consumes nearly 20% less electrical energy than the eAccess Gen1 with IBSG, allowing to enhance the autonomy of the vehicle.

4. Conclusion

e-Drive is one of the major set of components for the electric propulsion system. A Cooling system is necessary for the e-Drive, especially for the e-Motor to allow it to work efficiently and also to ensure the safety of the electrical components. The performance and efficiency of the e-Drive and the vehicle has strong proportionality with the cooling system and its integration. The proposed water glycol cooled system exhibits several desirable benefits over air cooled system. These include the significant improvements in cooling efficiency, maintenance simplicity, cost, etc. Off-the-shelf major components allow optimization of the production cost.

A PMSM motor is proposed due to its higher efficiency and higher torque density. Off-the-shelf major components such as rotor, stator is utilized in the e-Machine. A cooling control unit is embedded in the inverter to control the liquid flow rate depending on the information from temperature sensors mounted in different components of the e-Drive. Existing reducer is carried over and mounted in direct drive connection to the e-Machine to improve the NVH performance and reducer efficiency.

An active liquid (water+glycol) cooling system is integrated within the e-Drive, which notably enhances the cooling efficiency over air cooled previous solutions. A 1D simulation was performed in Modelon simulation software to size the cooling system, especially the heat sink. Finally, an e-Drive with integrated cooling system, simple mechanical and system interfaces was developed based on the Plug-and-Play approach. Finally, a simulation tool was developed in the matlab environment to simulate the performance and consumption.

The simulation results show that the proposed eAccess Gen2 with GMG provides significant improvements on both performance and consumption over existing eAccess Gen1 with IBSG and hence widens the potential application areas. The proposed eAccess powertrain thus has the potential for a significant global impact on electric propulsion systems.

5. Future works

Areas of future investigation include the development of CFD Simulation model for the cooling system and its implementation with the complete vehicle model to simulate the behavior closer to the real vehicle and comparing the simulation results with the road vehicle data. Furthermore, reduction ratio optimization is very important to find the best compromise between the performance and energy consumption. Another area to investigate includes more research into the feasibility of expanding and incorporating the proposed cooling system for the overall propulsion system including battery packs from both manufacturing and integration perspectives. In-vehicle Implementation would certainly help to validate the scope of the proposed eAccess.

6. Acknowledgements

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9. Annex

9.1 Tables

Table 1: Average power losses

7. References

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8. Glossary

Valeo-SVA: Valeo - Special Vehicle Applications
EV: Electric Vehicles
BEV: Battery Electric Vehicles
GMG: Gearbox Motor Generator
SMMG: Small Mobility Motor Generator
PMSM: Permanent Magnet Synchronous Machine
e-Motor: Electric Motor
e-Drive: Electric Drive
NVH: Noise, Vibration, Harshness
IP: Ingress Protection
ICE: Internal Combustion Engine
WW: World Wide
Gen: Generation
BSG: Belt Starter Generator
kWc: KiloWatt- Continuous
kWp: KiloWatt- Peak
WMTC: Worldwide Motorcycle Test Cycle
Conso: Consumption
Regen: Regeneration

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9.2 Figures

Figure 1: Worldwide EV market, 2021 H1 [Canalys]

Figure 2: Worldwide EV sales by Manufacturers [Canalys]

Figure 3: WW electrification forecast scenario [Bloomberg New Energy Finance, 2017]

Figure 4: eAccess Generation 1

Figure 5: eAccess Generation 2 (9 kW)

Figure 6: eAccess Gen2- Direct Drive, SMMG (4 kW)

Figure 7: Targeted eAccess Powertrain

Figure 8: e-Machine

Figure 9: Reducer

Figure 10: Inverter

Figure 11: Cooling system

Figure 12: WMTC2 driving cycle

Figure 13: Smart eAccess control system

Figure 14: eAccess Gen2- DD, GMG (13 kW)

Figure 15: eAccess Gen1 with IBSG

Figure 16: eAccess Ge2 with GMG